

The Managing Directors of Co-operative Sugar Factories In Karnataka and Maharashtra.

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Abstract :

The Managing Director is at the top level as he is the administrative head of all the officials of the factory in Karnataka and Maharashtra. The appointment procedure of Managing Director is differing from State to State. In Karnataka, the Managing Director is appointed by the state government. He is an I.A.S. or a KAS or a KCS officer from senior cadre. Since the officer is purely a State Government servant, the Board of Directors do not have control over him. This is not compulsory on the part of factories who have paid complete loan of Karnataka Government. But in Maharashtra, the Managing Director is appointed by the Board of Directors and he is not a State Government servant. While they enjoy certain facilities such as rent free housing, Servants, phone and vehicle, the Managing Directors in both the States are ex-officio members of the Board of Directors. In the State of Maharashtra, the panel of Managing Director is prepared on priority basis from the experts and scholars in the area of professional management. This promotes a favorable relation between the factory management and the Managing Director which in turn creates harmony in the decision making process. But in Karnataka the State Government nominates officers in most cases from any departments or from any category of officers. This practice of deputing officers without having even basic knowledge of sugar industries hamper the growth of sugar factories in Karnataka State. Moreover, he can use his dissent to any decision of the board. This absolves him of not being responsible for any act of the Board. For those acts the Board itself is responsible. Therefore it necessitates the factory management to keep in good contact with the Managing Director. In Karnataka the Managing Director participates in meetings and discussion and exercise vote while taking decision by the Board. But in Maharashtra, he participates in meetings and discussion and exercises vote as per will of the Chairman. It means he has no vote. The main duty is to have proper control and supervision over the affairs of the factories concerned. The Managing Director is a Chief Administrative Officer as well as an overall Public Relations Officer of the factories concerned. He acts according to the directions of the Board of Directors. But in Karnataka he has also some discretionary powers like, administrative financial (sanctioning amount) appointment of staff, share allotment etc. because he is a State Government servant and he safeguards the interest of State Government also. In Karnataka he holds office normally, for a period of 4 years and his services may be recalled by the parent government. But in Maharashtra he holds office up to the retirement or bond period or until he had the confidence of the Board of Directors. He has to act as a friend, philosopher and guide to the factory. As such he has to make efforts towards increasing the productivity of co-operative enterprise by motivating the employees for better performance.

The Managing Director plays a very important role in the factory concerned for its development. Since he occupies a significant position in a sugar factory, he has to maintain good relations with Board of Directors and also to get the best results out of a team of technical heads.

In Karnataka there are always frequent transfers of the officers holding the post of the Managing director in sugar factory because of following reasons.

1. General transfers by the State Government or request for transfer. Officer wants to opt out because they can get higher posts like District Commissioner, Registrar etc.

2. Retirement

3. Promotions

4. Expiry of agreed term of the deputation.

In Maharashtra there are no frequent transfer/ changes of the officers holding the post of the Managing Directors in sugar factory, because he is appointed by the Board of Directors. He is supposed to act according to the wishes of the Board as the State Government has no power to meddle with his appointment.

Powers and Functions of the Managing Director:

The powers and functions of the Managing Directors of the factories are more or less the same in Karnataka and Maharashtra. The Managing Director may remove from the muster-roll the name of any workman, if he

is unauthorized remaining absent for more than 10 consecutive days, by treating him as having left the service. He may also issue charge sheets to the employees and appoint enquiry officers to conduct enquiries for any act of misconduct of the employees. However, there are hardly few cases of removal of workmen from the muster-roll by the Managing Director. The specific powers and functions of Managing Director are as follows

1. To control and supervise day-to-day administration of the sugar factory.
2. To sanction amount for establishments, purchase of stores and other contingent expenditure.
3. To maintain proper accounts of the factory.
4. To represent in all legal actions instituted by or against the society.
5. The Managing Director may delegate any of his powers to the officers subordinate to him subject to the approval of the Board of Directors.
6. To draw, accept endorse and negotiate bills of exchange and endorse bill, transfer or otherwise deal with shares and Government securities.
7. The Managing Director shall be responsible for convening the meetings of the Board of Directors and the Executive Committee In consultation with the Chairman or in his absence the Vice Chairman. He shall also be responsible to call for the meeting of the General body as and when directed by the Board or on receipt of requisition from requisite number of members or a requisition from the Registrar of Co-operative Societies of respective States.
8. It shall be the duty of the Managing Director to send the notice the meetings along with agenda, which shall clearly specify the time, date and place of the meeting.
9. The Managing Director should record the proceedings of all kind of meetings and has to sign along with the Chairman at the end of the proceedings.
10. To see that the audit report is placed before the Board/ Committee for their consideration and to take steps in regard to rectification and submission of the audit rectification report.
11. To issue share certificate to the members signed by the Chairman and 2 Directors including the Managing Director.

12. To carry on correspondence and to supply all needful information to the members through the Chairman.

13. Any other assignment entrusted by the Chairman/Board of Directors connected with the factory.

The comparative study of powers and functions of Managing Directors in the States shows that the Managing Director of Co-operative sugar factories in Karnataka State is more powerful than the Managing Director of co-operative sugar factories of Maharashtra. Even in financial matters, the Managing Director of Maharashtra is not powerful but the Managing Director in Karnataka is more powerful and he is accustomed to use his discretionary powers. In Karnataka, for every act the signature of the Managing Director is essential and he can act according to his discretionary power in the interest of State Government. Whereas in Maharashtra, the Managing Director has to act according to the will of the Board of Directors. It means Managing Director is only a figurehead and acting as a puppet of Board of Directors. In Karnataka, the Managing Director has to safeguard the interest of Government, farmers, labourers rather than Board of Directors. But in Karnataka there is a possibility of clash between the Managing Director and the Board of Directors as he is deputed from the State Government. Whereas in Maharashtra there is less possibility of clash between the Managing Director and the Board of Directors at the time of exercising their powers and discharging their functions as the Managing Director generally safeguards the interest of Board of Directors. The Managing Director of cooperative sugar factories of Maharashtra had more control on labourers and officers of the factory rather than the Managing Director of Karnataka cooperative sugar factories.

References:

1. Dr. N. R. Patil, Comparative Study of cooperative sugar factory Karnataka and Maharashtra. Chiranjeev Publication Bhojwadi. 2007
2. Goel S.L., Goel, B.B., Principles, problems and prospects of co-operative administration, sterling New Delhi, 1979
3. By-laws of the cooperative sugar factories of Karnataka and Maharashtra.
4. Personal observation and interview with the Managing Directors of cooperative sugar factories of Karnataka and Maharashtra.